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Epidemiology of Intussusception hospitalizations in children under 2 years of age post rotavirus vaccine introduction in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	Abstract Purpose High burden of rotavirus associated diarrhea has been documented among Indian children. The

phased introduction of an indigenous rotavirus vaccine 'ROTAVAC' in India's national immunization programme began in 2017. Phase III trial showed the vaccine to have a low intussusception risk profile. However, evaluation of post-licensure trends of intussusception is necessary to assess potential vaccine-associated intussusception risk. This study's objective was to describe the epidemiology of intussusception hospitalizations in children under 2 years of age in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry following ROTAVAC introduction.

Methods

A cross-sectional surveillance was established in six hospitals in Tamil-Nadu and Puducherry. Children under two years of age with intussusception fulfilling Brighton Collaboration's criteria for level 1 diagnostic certainty were enrolled. Patient and disease characteristics were captured using a standardized questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were performed using Stata Version 13.

Results

Overall, 287 cases were enrolled and had a median age of seven months. Frequently presenting symptoms were vomiting (78%), abdominal pain (76%) and blood in stool (71%). Abdominal ultrasonography or radiography confirmed diagnosis in 65% of cases and managed by nonoperative measures. Remaining 35% of cases were diagnosed and managed with surgery. Over 98% of the cases had positive treatment outcomes. Age less than five months (OR=4.36), and hospitalization at a state government health facility (OR=5.01) were significant predictors for children to receive surgical management.

Conclusions

Our study documents the epidemiology of intussusceptions immediately after the rollout of rotavirus vaccine in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry. No appreciable increase in intussusception hospitalizations was seen in the study hospitals after vaccine introduction.

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Abstract (250 words)

Purpose

High burden of rotavirus associated diarrhea has been documented among Indian children. The phased introduction of an indigenous rotavirus vaccine 'ROTAVAC' in India's national immunization programme began in 2017. Phase III trial showed the vaccine to have a low intussusception risk profile. However, evaluation of post-licensure trends of intussusception is necessary to assess potential vaccine-associated intussusception risk. This study's objective was to describe the epidemiology of intussusception hospitalizations in children under 2 years of age in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry following ROTAVAC introduction.

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Keywords: India, Intussusception, Puducherry, Rotavirus vaccination, ROTAVAC, Tamil Nadu

Introduction

1 Intussusception is a common cause of intestinal obstruction in infancy and childhood; the
2 majority of cases being idiopathic [1]. Diagnosis of intussusception is made by
3 ultrasonography, radiology or at surgery, and cases are mostly managed with non-operative
4 techniques of pneumatic or hydrostatic reductions. However, in complicated cases or on the
5 failure of non-operative reduction, surgery is usually required and may involve either manual
6 reduction or intestinal resection in patients presenting with vascular compromise or perforation
7 or pathological lead point [1, 2]. The estimated median annual incidence of intussusception
8 globally ranges from 34 (African region) to 90 (Western Pacific region) per 100 000 children
9 aged less than one year [3]. In South-East Asia, the estimated incidence is 90 per 100 000
10 children aged <1 year and 52 per 100 000 children aged <5 years. There is a paucity of
11 intussusception incidence data in India. Studies from Delhi and Chandigarh has reported an
12 estimated 17.7 and 20 cases respectively per 100 000 infant-years [4, 5].
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24 Rotavirus is a major cause of severe diarrhoea requiring hospitalization in young children
25 worldwide [6]. The first licenced rotavirus vaccine 'Rotashield[®]' was withdrawn in the USA,
26 following its association with an increased incidence of intussusception among vaccinated
27 children [7]. Consequently, the association of intussusception with rotavirus vaccines was
28 closely studied, when newer rotavirus vaccines - Rotarix[®] and Rotateq[®] were introduced in
29 several countries [7]. In India, data on the high burden of rotavirus-associated diarrhoea in
30 children under 5 years of age was generated between 2005 and 2016 by several studies
31 including two rounds of national-level multi-centric rotavirus surveillance [8, 9]. Availability
32 of robust data on rotavirus associated diarrhoea contributed to the introduction of an
33 indigenously developed monovalent rotavirus vaccine, ROTAVAC[®] in the national
34 immunization programme in select states and union territories of India including Tamil Nadu
35 and Puducherry [10, 11].
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47 Despite the low intussusception risk demonstrated by the vaccine in trial settings, it was
48 essential to monitor the level of intussusception, post-vaccine introduction. For evaluating
49 post-licensure trends of intussusception and assessing any potential vaccine-associated risk,
50 geographically representative baseline data on intussusception was necessary. Towards
51 generating this data, prospective surveillance of intussusception was established in six hospitals
52 in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry. In this report, we describe the epidemiologic features of
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intussusception among under two-year-old children following the introduction of the rotavirus vaccine in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry, South India.

Material and Methods

Study design

This is a prospective, cross-sectional multi-site evaluation of intussusception conducted between June 2017 and September 2019 at five sentinel hospitals in Tamil Nadu (Christian Medical College and Hospital, Vellore; Institute of Child Health and Hospital for Children, Chennai; Kanchi Kamakoti Childs Trust Hospital, Chennai; Government Medical College, Madurai and Government Medical College, Coimbatore) and one in Puducherry (Jawaharlal Institute of Post-Graduate Medical Education & Research) (Fig. 1). Details of site selection and surveillance initiation has been previously published [12].

Study population

Children under two years of age with suspected intussusception admitted to the participating sentinel hospitals were eligible for enrollment into surveillance. Inclusion criteria for case enrolment were i) age below 2 years, and ii) fulfilling Brighton collaboration criteria for level 1 diagnostic certainty for intussusception i.e., confirmation during surgery and/ or by specific radiologic findings (reduction by pneumatic/ hydrostatic/ contrast enema) or specific characteristics on sonography or at autopsy [13].

Data collection

Surveillance staff identified hospitalized intussusception cases by visiting pediatric in-patient wards and reviewing admission and surgical theatre logs. The eligibility of each case was ascertained by the study physician prior to enrollment. For each enrolled child, a case report form was filled and a copy of the ultrasound report along with image, hospital procedure/ treatment notes, and a copy of the vaccination record was collected. The enrolment activity was carried out in close coordination with the pediatric surgeons and radiologists in the participating hospitals. Monitoring of surveillance activity at each sentinel site was carried out once in 3 months, and performance was evaluated using a monitoring checklist.

Data analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using Stata Version 13 (StataCorp, College Station, TX, USA). Descriptive analyses of demographic, clinical, and treatment characteristics were carried out. The median (with IQR) was calculated for continuous variables whereas proportions and frequency tables were used to summarize categorical variables. Univariate logistic regression analysis followed by multivariable logistic regression model was adopted to identify predictors of different treatment modalities. Variables of known clinical or contextual importance were used for the multivariable regression model.

Ethics

The study was approved by the institutional review boards/ ethics committees of each participating hospital/ institution. Written informed consent was obtained from parents/ guardians of eligible children prior to enrolment in the surveillance.

Results

Socio-Demographic characteristics

During the period of surveillance, 287 intussusception cases matching the Brighton's collaboration level I diagnostic certainty was admitted and managed at the participating hospitals. Median age (interquartile range) of cases was 7 (6-12) and 74% of them were aged <1 year (Table 1). We found a unimodal age distribution with a peak in children aged 4-10 months (Fig. 2). The male-to-female ratio was 2.8:1 and ranged between 1:1 in Vellore and 2.8:1 in Madurai. Intussusception hospitalizations were seen throughout the year in all participating hospitals. About 50% of cases had received one or more doses of rotavirus vaccination.

Clinical characteristics, diagnosis and treatment modalities

The most frequent presenting symptoms were vomiting (78%), abdominal pain (76%) and Blood in stool (71%) (Table 1). The classic triad of bloody stool, vomiting and abdominal pain was found in 125 (43.6%) patients. The median duration between onset of the symptom(s) and admission to any of the surveillance hospitals was 1 day (IQR, 1-2), with 42% of the cases being referrals from other hospitals. There was no significant association of the presence of classical triad among cases with either time to hospitalization from symptom(s) onset ($p = 0.703$) or duration of hospitalization ($p=0.061$). Abdominal ultrasonography or radiography confirmed diagnosis in 65% of cases whereas, in 36% cases, intussusception was diagnosed on

1 surgery. The frequency of using radiography and/ ultrasonography procedures did not differ
2 among the study hospitals except in Madurai and Chennai where a large proportion of cases
3 were diagnosed at surgery. A reduction of intussusception by non-operative measures was
4 possible in 65% of cases. In the remaining 35% of cases, surgical procedure i.e. manual
5 reduction (30%) or resection (5%) was performed. There was no significant association
6 between the type of treatment received and the day of presentation to the hospital (Fig. 3).
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10 ***Location of Intussusception, treatment outcomes***

11 The most common location of intussusception was ileocolic (88%), followed by ileoileal (2%),
12 colocolic (1%), and compound (6%). In 3% of cases, information on the location was not
13 available. In 3.5% of cases, complications such as wound infection (2.5%), secondary intestinal
14 obstruction (0.7%) and peritonitis (0.3%) was seen. Overall, the median duration of hospital
15 stay was 2 days (IQR 1-6) but it was higher in Madurai, Chennai, and Coimbatore (Table 1).
16 Except for five cases, all other children (98%) had good outcomes and were discharged. Three
17 of the deaths were from Madurai whereas the remaining two were from the public sector
18 hospital in Chennai. Among the five cases, four were male children and the median time to
19 hospitalization for the five cases was 3 days whereas the median length of hospitalization was
20 13 days. All five cases had either surgical reduction or resection and two of them had peritonitis
21 (n=1) and wound infection (n=2).
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35 ***Predictors of treatment modalities***

36 We also investigated predictors of treatment (surgery vs non-surgical intervention) using
37 Univariate and multivariable logistic regression analysis (Table 2.). Age 0-5 months [OR=4.36,
38 CI= (1.46-13.05)] and hospitalization at a state government health facility [OR=5.01, CI=(2.29-
39 10.98)] were the significant predictors for children to receive surgical management (Fig. 3).
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46 **Discussion**

47 Initiation of the phased introduction of the Rotavirus vaccine in 2016 was an important
48 milestone in the national immunization program in India. As part of the efforts that were made
49 to study the impact of the rotavirus vaccine rollout, active hospital-based surveillance for
50 intussusception was established in many of the vaccine introducer states including Tamil Nadu
51 and Puducherry. We describe the findings of over two years of intussusception surveillance
52 involving five sentinel hospitals in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry. Intussusception is known to
53 occur more commonly among males. The proportion of males diagnosed with intussusception
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in the present study was higher than that of females, which is consistent with previous reports from India [14-17]. The classical triad of abdominal pain, vomiting and blood in stools was seen only in 44% of the total cases. This was higher than 6.4% - 29.6% seen in recent reports from India [14,16 -18].

In this study, intussusception was commonly seen during the first year of life, with a higher proportion of cases 6 - 12 months age category. The number of cases rose from 3 months of age and peaked at around 6 months before decreasing gradually. Similar age trends were documented in previous studies from India [14-17]. Admissions of intussusception cases were seen throughout the year in all participating hospitals without any appreciable seasonality. A similar trend in the occurrence of intussusception cases has been documented in other studies in India [14, 15, 17].

A review of studies reporting intussusception between 2002 and 2012 showed a low rate of surgical management from studies in Asia [19]. One-thirds of cases in our study undergoing surgical intervention and this finding is comparable with more recent studies in India wherein higher surgical rates (39% -72%) are reported. Delay in seeking medical attention or delay in referral to an appropriate health facility is usually considered the reason for severe cases requiring surgical intervention. However, in our study, the median time to hospitalization was short and hence there may be other factors such as non-availability of radiologists/ sonologists 24x7 etc. that needs to further analysed to enable non-surgical management to be attempted in all eligible cases. This will reduce surgery associated morbidity and complications as well as avert prolonged hospital stays, all of which impose a considerable economic burden on the patients and the health system provided infrastructure and expertise for non-operative reduction is available. The low proportion of deaths in the present study is comparable to previous reports from India and Asia [15-17, 19].

The current recommendation of rotavirus vaccination in India is at ages 6, 10 and 14 weeks [20]. In this study, very few cases were seen among under three months olds whereas about one-fourth of cases were in 3-6 months age category. Currently, in the vaccination programme, administration of the rotavirus vaccine is permitted until one year of age [20]. Continued monitoring of trends in intussusception case burden across the country with a larger sample is necessary to document the impact of rotavirus vaccination on background rates of intussusception in India. The current study was limited only to intussusception cases admitted

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to select hospitals, most of which were tertiary level hospitals. Thus, not all cases in the study population/ region were captured in this surveillance and the catchment population of the study hospitals could also not be defined, making incidence rate estimation not possible.

The present study is one of the early reports on epidemiology of intussusception hospitalizations in post-rotavirus vaccine introduction scenario in India and the first report from Tamil Nadu and Puducherry.

Conclusion

Our study documents the epidemiology of intussusceptions immediately after the rollout of rotavirus vaccine in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry. Though no appreciable increase in intussusception hospitalizations was seen in the study hospitals after vaccine introduction, continued monitoring of intussusception rates is necessary to monitor safety profiles of the current as well as newer rotavirus vaccines in the national immunization programme.

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Disclosure

The findings and conclusions in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the official position of the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation or US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

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Authors contributions

Acquisition of data – All authors

Analysis of data – SR, GCP, KS, SS, NS, VT

Interpretation of data – SR, KS, GCP, SBS, NS, BHK, KM, RP, GG

Drafting of the article – GCP, AS, PD, MJ

Critically revising drafts of the article – KS, GCP, SBS, NS

Final approval of submitted version – All authors

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Conflict of Interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Availability of data and material (data transparency):

Anonymized datasets can be provided on request.

Code availability (software application or custom code):

Codes will be provided on request.

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Legends

Table 1. Patient characteristics and clinical course of intussusception cases: 2016-2019

Table 2: Logistic regression model for predictors of treatment type among children under two years of age admitted with intussusception

Fig.1 Map showing location of hospitals under surveillance

Fig. 2 Age distribution of intussusception hospitalizations among children <2 years of age (2016-2019)

Table 1. Patient characteristics and clinical course of intussusception cases: 2016-2019

Clinical course	CMC VEL*	GMC CBE	GMC MDU	ICH CHE	JIPMER PY	KKCTH CHE	Total
Number (%)	38(13)	18(6)	23(8)	93(33)	38(13)	77(27)	287(100)
Age							
0-2months	0	0	0	1(1.1)	0	1(1.3)	2(0.7)
3-5months	5(13)	5(28)	8(35)	17(18)	11(29)	21(27)	67(23)
6-11months	27(71)	7(39)	9(39)	39(42)	19(50)	41(53)	142(49)
12-23months	6(16)	6(33)	6(26)	36(39)	8(21)	14(18)	76(26)
Age in months, median (IQR)	7(5-10)	7(5-14)	6(4-10)	7(5-10)	7(5-11)	6(4-10)	7(6-12)
Sex							
Male	19(50)	12(67)	17(74)	62(67)	23(61)	47(61)	180(63)
Female	19(50)	6(33)	6(26)	31(33)	15(39)	30(39)	107(37)
Clinical symptoms							
Diarrhoea	15(39)	6(33)	9(39)	26(28)	26(68)	22(29)	104(36)
vomiting	35(92)	10(56)	18(78)	77(83)	30(79)	54(70)	224(78)
fever	6(16)	2(11)	8(35)	23(25)	7(18)	12(16)	58(20)
Blood in stool	31(82)	8(44)	18(78)	73(79)	29(76)	46(60)	205(71)
Abdominal Pain	19(50)	12(67)	19(83)	64(69)	38(100)	66(86)	218(76)
Classical Triad	14(37)	4(22)	12(52)	43(46)	23(61)	29(38)	125(44)
Diagnosis Level of Criteria							
Radiological 1	6(16)	0	0	6(7)	2(5)	8(10)	22(8)
Radiological-USG	23(60)	14(78)	1(5)	41(44)	26(68)	58(75)	163(57)
Surgical	9(24)	4(22)	22(95)	46(49)	10(27)	11(15)	102(35)
Treatment method							
Pneumatic /Hydrostatic reduction	29(76)	14(78)	1(5)	47(51)	28(74)	66(86)	185(65)
Surgery without resection	9(24)	3(17)	18(78)	41(44)	5(13)	11(14)	87(30)
Surgery with resection	0	1(5)	4(17)	5(5)	5(13)	0(0)	15(5)
Outcome							
Discharged home	38(100)	18(100)	20(87)	91(98)	38(100)	77(100)	282(98)
Died	0(0)	0	3(13)	2(2)	0		5(2)
Duration of hospitalization in days, median (IQR)	1(1-3)	3(2-5)	10(7- 13)	4(2-6)	1(1-4)	2(1-2)	2(1-6)
Time between onset of symptoms and admission (Treating Hospital) in days, median (IQR)	1(1-2)	1(0-1)	2(0-3)	1(1-2)	1(0-2)	1(1-2)	1(1-2)
No. of Referral presentations	31(82)	0	18(78)	28(30)	2(5)	40(52)	119(42)
Location of intussusception							
ileocolic	30(79)	18(100)	22(96)	80(86)	31(82)	71(92)	252(88)

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64	65							
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903	904	905	906	907	908	909	910	911
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921	922	923	924	925	926	927	928	929
930	931	932	933	934	935	936	937	938
939	940	941	942	943	944	945	946	947
948	949	950	951	952	953	954	955	956
957	958	959	960	961	962	963	964	965
966	967	968	969	970	971	972	973	974
975	976	977	978	979	980	981	982	983
984	985	986	987	988	989	990	991	992
993	994	995	996	997	998	999	1000	1001

*VEL: Vellore; CBE: Coimbatore; MDU: Madurai; CHE: Chennai; PY: Puducherry

Table 2: Logistic regression model for predictors of treatment type among children under two years of age admitted with intussusception

Variables	Category	Hy/Py reduction n (%)	Surgical procedure n (%)	Odds ratio (95% CI)	p value	AOR (95% CI)	p value
Age	0-5 months	32 (46%)	37 (54%)	2.49 (1.38-4.5)	0.002	4.36 (1.46-13.05)*	0.009
	6-11 months	97 (68%)	45 (32%)	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	12-23 months	56 (74%)	20 (26%)	0.77 (0.41-1.43)	0.409	0.79 (0.29-2.14)	0.643
Blood in stools	No	61 (75%)	20 (25%)	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Yes	124 (60%)	81 (40%)	1.99 (1.12-3.55)	0.019	1.3 (0.44-3.79)	0.642
Classical triad	No	113(70)	49(30)	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Yes	72(58)	53(42)	1.69 (1.04-2.77)	0.034	1.09 (0.44-2.72)	0.849
Treatment facility	Private	95 (83%)	20 (17%)	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Govt- state	62(46%)	72(54%)	5.52 (3.06-9.95)	<0.001	5.01 (2.29-10.98)*	<0.001
Age at start of other milk (n=172)	Central Institutes	28(74%)	10(26%)	1.7 (.71-4.04)	0.233	0.77 (0.14-4.35)	0.765
	1-3 months	15 (43%)	20 (57%)	5.09 (1.98-13.07)	0.001	1.77 (0.53-5.88)	0.353
	4-6 months	48 (67%)	24 (33%)	1.91 (0.84-4.36)	0.125	1.08 (0.42-2.79)	0.875
	7-9 months	42 (79%)	11 (21%)	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	>9 months	11 (92%)	1 (8%)	0.35 (0.04-2.99)	0.335	0.35 (0.04-3.48)	0.372

Hy/Pn: Hydrostatic/ Pneumatic reduction; Govt: Government; *p-value <0.05

Fig.1 Map showing location of hospitals under surveillance

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Fig. 2 Age distribution of intussusception hospitalizations among children <2 years of age (2016-2019)

Fig. 3 Treatment modality according to A) Day of presentation B) Type of health care facility

Title Page

Epidemiology of Intussusception hospitalizations in children under 2 years of age post rotavirus vaccine introduction in Tamil Nadu and Puducherry

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Acquisition of data – All authors

Analysis of data – SR, GCP, KS, SS, NS, VT

Interpretation of data – SR, KS, GCP, SBS, NS, BHK, KM, RP, GG

Drafting of the article – GCP, AS, PD, MJ

Critically revising drafts of the article – KS, GCP, SBS, NS

Final approval of submitted version – All authors

Ethics approval

Ethical Clearance has been obtained by each of the participating institutes from their respective Ethical Clearance Committees/Institute Review Boards.

Consent to participate And Consent for publication

Consent for participation and for publication and sharing of data have been obtained from the guardians of each of the participants (cases and controls) prior to enrolment in the study by each of the participating institutes

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Availability of data and material (data transparency):

Anonymized datasets can be provided on request.

Code availability (software application or custom code):

Codes will be provided on request.

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Figure 2

Figure 3

Table1

Clinical course	CMC VEL*	GMC CBE	GMC MDU	ICH CHE	JIPMER PY	KKCTH CHE	Total
Number (%)	38(13)	18(6)	23(8)	93(33)	38(13)	77(27)	287(100)
Age							
0-2months	0	0	0	1(1.1)	0	1(1.3)	2(0.7)
3-5months	5(13)	5(28)	8(35)	17(18)	11(29)	21(27)	67(23)
6-11months	27(71)	7(39)	9(39)	39(42)	19(50)	41(53)	142(49)
12-23months	6(16)	6(33)	6(26)	36(39)	8(21)	14(18)	76(26)
Age in months, median (IQR)	7(5-10)	7(5-14)	6(4-10)	7(5-10)	7(5-11)	6(4-10)	7(6-12)
Sex							
Male	19(50)	12(67)	17(74)	62(67)	23(61)	47(61)	180(63)
Female	19(50)	6(33)	6(26)	31(33)	15(39)	30(39)	107(37)
Clinical symptoms							
Diarrhoea	15(39)	6(33)	9(39)	26(28)	26(68)	22(29)	104(36)
vomiting	35(92)	10(56)	18(78)	77(83)	30(79)	54(70)	224(78)
fever	6(16)	2(11)	8(35)	23(25)	7(18)	12(16)	58(20)
Blood in stool	31(82)	8(44)	18(78)	73(79)	29(76)	46(60)	205(71)
Abdominal Pain	19(50)	12(67)	19(83)	64(69)	38(100)	66(86)	218(76)
Classical Triad	14(37)	4(22)	12(52)	43(46)	23(61)	29(38)	125(44)
Diagnosis Level of Criteria							
Radiological 1	6(16)	0	0	6(7)	2(5)	8(10)	22(8)
Radiological-USG	23(60)	14(78)	1(5)	41(44)	26(68)	58(75)	163(57)
Surgical	9(24)	4(22)	22(95)	46(49)	10(27)	11(15)	102(35)
Treatment method							
Pneumatic /Hydrostatic reduction	29(76)	14(78)	1(5)	47(51)	28(74)	66(86)	185(65)
Surgery without resection	9(24)	3(17)	18(78)	41(44)	5(13)	11(14)	87(30)
Surgery with resection	0	1(5)	4(17)	5(5)	5(13)	0(0)	15(5)
Outcome							
Discharged home	38(100)	18(100)	20(87)	91(98)	38(100)	77(100)	282(98)
Died	0(0)	0	3(13)	2(2)	0		5(2)
Duration of hospitalization in days, median (IQR)	1(1-3)	3(2-5)	10(7- 13)	4(2-6)	1(1-4)	2(1-2)	2(1-6)
Time between onset of symptoms and admission (Treating Hospital) in days, median (IQR)	1(1-2)	1(0-1)	2(0-3)	1(1-2)	1(0-2)	1(1-2)	1(1-2)

No. of Referral presentations	31(82)	0	18(78)	28(30)	2(5)	40(52)	119(42)
Location of intussusception							
ileocolic	30(79)	18(100)	22(96)	80(86)	31(82)	71(92)	252(88)
Colo-colic	1(3)			2(2)	0	1(1)	4(1)
Ileo-ileal	2(5)		1(4)	2(2)		1(1)	6(2)
Compound	2(5)			8(9)	7(18)		17(6)
Unknown	3(8)			1(1)		4(6)	8(3)
Complication							
Wound infection	2(5)	0	1(4)	1(1)	3(8)	0	7(2.5)
peritonitis				1(1)			1(0.3)
Secondary intestinal obstruction		2(11)					2(0.7)

*VEL: Vellore; CBE: Coimbatore; MDU: Madurai; CHE: Chennai; PY: Puducherry

Table 2

Variables	Category	Hy/Py reduction n (%)	Surgical procedure n (%)	Odds ratio (95% CI)	p value	AOR (95% CI)	p value
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Hy/Pn: Hydrostatic/ Pneumatic reduction; Govt: Government; *p-value <0.05